

A Research Report

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TRW
SURVEY

**Impact of Clubs and Department
on Placement Scenario
at BITS Goa**

To
Prof. Shalini Upadhyay
For partial fulfilment of the requirements of
BITS F112, Technical Report Writing

Abstract

BITS - Pilani, Goa houses more than fifty clubs and departments, which are managed by students themselves. The students, apart from spending their quality time on academic courses, also participate in these clubs and departments. The present report aims to investigate the impact of these clubs and departments on students' placements.

The present study has been taken to find out the impact of clubs and departments on academics, career prospects of students, and to identify the scope for further improvement. The survey was conducted in April 2020 and three groups of respondents (junior undergraduates - first and second year students; senior undergraduates - third and fourth year students; and alumni of BITS-Pilani, Goa) were selected and called up through WhatsApp and LinkedIn.

In all, 150 responses were received, within the given time frame, and analysed using stratified sampling method. A comprehensive assessment has been made to identify those skills that are gathered by a student from these clubs and departments, and prove helpful in placement. A corresponding feedback was taken from the student representatives, working in placement unit, to verify the present observations.

On the grounds of responses received from students, alumni and representatives of placement unit, some significant conclusions have been drawn and recommendations have been forwarded to improve the placement scenario at BITS-Pilani Goa. The present report calls for further inquiry into the mechanism that can improve the placement scenario of the campus.

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Chapter 1 | Introduction

Clubs and departments have been an integral part of BITS Pilani, Goa Campus since its inception in 2004. They were primarily formed by the students with an objective to break the monotony of the regular course curriculum and to promote extra-curricular activities amongst students on campus.

Gradually this objective started to get broader and it also included those departments that managed fests, and the clubs that promoted technical projects, helping in implementation of the knowledge acquired through regular academics.

Today, clubs and departments have become an inseparable part of student's campus life. Students invest much of their time in these activities for various reasons, one of them being that clubs and departments lead to a good placement. However, this may eventually reflect on their academic performance.

The influence of student organisations, clubs and departments, in the development of leadership traits, has been a subject of critical investigation among researchers. In order to assess whether extracurricular activity is a boon or bane in students' life, studies were carried out on total extracurricular activity participation (TEAP) in US and it was observed that the total extracurricular activity participation had positive correlation with senior and post-secondary outcomes (**Marsh, 1992**).

Another attempt was made to observe, if participation in extracurricular activities during leisure time helps in the construction of pathways. During the study, transition from school to work was intensely examined, employing quantitative and qualitative data (**Merino, 2007**). Further studies on students' perception regarding the role of higher education credentials for graduate work and employability, depicted that being active in

group activities, other than pure academics, could enhance job possibilities. Those university graduates who participated in clubs and departments found jobs conforming to their qualifications more easily than their fellow students who did not participate in such activities. Further, they had access to larger firms and better managerial positions after graduation (**Tomlinson, 2008**).

A number of studies point towards the fact that extracurricular societies, allow students to work in close communion with fellow students, faculty and administration thereby, serve as catalyst for developing student leadership. Extracurricular activities help to mobilize students from passive to active roles, and thus, instil a culture of responsibility, empowerment and community service (**Veronesi and Gunderman, 2012**). But do the students take part in clubs and activities for sake of better academic outcomes, leadership or placement?

In an investigation to understand students' interest in activities related to clubs and departments, it was found that 80.2% students reported were involved in at least one extra-curricular department. Initially, the students participated in such activities out of their intrinsic drives, but later, they started getting influenced by external motives, to demonstrate competencies that are otherwise invisible in resumé, or due to the increasing pressure of finding a job after graduation (**Roulin & Bangerter, 2012**).

Some investigators developed a statistical model determine the correlation between student leadership and employment opportunities. The impact of extra-curricular merits on hiring outcome was evident from their result, according to which, academic performance and extra-curricular engagement, such as being part of various student organisations, enhanced the job prospects by about 7% (**Verhaest and Baert, 2018**).

These studies have predominantly targeted on leadership and job prospects only. However, none of them dealt upon the need of professional skills, like team work, time management, prioritization, working autonomy or self-confidence, interpersonal skills, creative thinking, problem solving and communication skills, that are important for any placement activity. Moreover, these results do not stand valid in a scenario where a good number of students, join various clubs and departments and remain passive for most of the activity period. Thus, clubs and departments are necessary, but to what extent, is another point of concern. The present study has been taken to bridge these gaps and to find out: i) the impact of clubs and department on academics; ii) the impact of clubs and department on future prospects; and iii) the scope for further improvement.

In all, three questionnaires were prepared, one for each group. The first group comprised junior undergraduates (first- and second- year students); second group involved senior undergraduates (third- and fourth year students); and the third group consisted of alumni. Questionnaires were floated through Google forms to students on WhatsApp and alumni on LinkedIn. Of the two hundred students and alumni contacted, 150 responded to the questionnaire which comprised 92 junior undergraduates, 31 senior undergraduates and 27 alumni. The sampling method used, in the present survey, was similar to the stratified sampling method/ purposive sampling method.

The placement unit could not be contacted directly due to COVID-19 lockdown, and hence, the responses from the experienced student representatives, were obtained through WhatsApp. The responses so received, were analysed to compare their perception with that of students and alumni.

Analysis was done after scrutiny of the responses obtained from the three groups and the placement unit. Deductions were made to ascertain whether the skills gained by students in clubs and departments were helpful or detrimental in placement activities.

The present report includes a brief description of each club, together with its functions and respective verticals. Thereafter, impact of clubs and departments on academic performance, requisites for a good placement, and alumni's perspective on effect of clubs and departments on placement have been dealt with. Subsequently, an all-inclusive comparison has been attempted between those skills that are acquired by the students through participation at various levels in these clubs and departments and the skills that are essential for placement. On the basis of foregoing results, certain significant conclusions have been derived and recommendations have been compiled to enhance the placement scenario at BITS-Pilani Goa.

The present report has been prepared in partial fulfilment of the requirements of BITS F112, Technical Report Writing. It indicates the influence of clubs and departments on academic performance of the undergraduate students, acquisition of professional skills, and the placement output of the campus. It stimulates an inquiry to enlist those factors that have been instrumental in creating a favourable environment for placements at BITS-Pilani, Goa and those which can further enhance placement activities in the campus.

Chapter 2 | Clubs and Departments in BITS Goa

2.1 Technical Clubs

S No	Name of the Club	Functions
1	Electronics and Robotics Club	: develops electronic and robotics projects
2	Aerodynamics (AeroD)	: develops drones and conducts workshops
3	Computer Graphics (CG)	: develops 3D models
4	Society of Automotive Engineers	: develops cars and automotive machinery
5	Developer's Society (DevSoc)	: develops apps for phone
6	SEDS Celestia	: conducts night sky-watching sessions
7	Wallstreet	: conducts regular classes on finance; events during Quark and Waves
8	Centre for Entrepreneurial Leadership (CEL)	: promotes entrepreneur culture on campus; organizes Coalescence
9	Environmental Protection and Awareness Club (EPAC)	: makes people aware about Nature conservation; organizes bird watching

Besides, there are Astro Club, Coding Club, Matrix, Robocon, Inspired Karters, Shell Eco Marathon and so on.

2.2 Non-technical Clubs

S No.	Name of the Club	: Functions
1	<i>Kala</i>	: club of artistic people; performs in fests
2	Fashion Club (Fash Club)	: performs a 30 min show during Waves
3	Drama Club	: performs Hindi and English Dramas
4	Music Society (MuSoc)	: organizes music nights
5	Dance Club	: conducts dance events

6	Mime	: performs in Orientations and Farewells
7	Synchrnoise	: performs vocal singing during fests
8	Filmmaking (FMaC)	: makes short films for YouTube
9	180 Degrees Consulting	: India's 3 rd largest '180° Consulting' club
10	Quiz Club	: conducts BQL and quizzes during fests
11	Trekking Club	: organizes trekking every semester
12	<i>Srutilaya</i>	: organizes classic dance and music shows
13	Literary and Debating Club	: organizes literary events, quiz, debates
14	<i>Abhivyakti</i>	: organizes Hindi poetry sessions

In addition, the campus comprises ArBits, BITS Pilani Consulting Club, Creative Activities Club (CrAC), English Language Activities Society (ELAS), Gaming Club, Hindi Activities Society (HAS), Radio Control Club etc.

2.3 Departments

S No	Name of the Department	Functions
1	Department of Stage Controls	: arranges speakers and lights during fests
2	Department of Photography (DoPy)	: captures all the events round the year
3	Department of Surveillance and Registration (DoSaR)	: responsible for registration of students in all events and managing discipline
4	Department of Sponsorship and Marketing (DoSM)	: responsible for generating sponsorships for events and fests
5	Department of Publicity and PR	: manages publicity
6	Department of Professional Nights	: organises night events
7	Department of Creative Works	: organizes creative events during fests
8	Department of Journalism and Media Affairs (DoJMA)	: responsible for media coverage
9	Department of Arts n Decorations	: responsible for theme and decoration

10	Department of Media and Coverage	: prepares and releases press notes
11	Department of Finance and Asset Management (DoFAM)	: responsible for allocation and supervision of funds and assets
12	BITSMUN	: organizes MUN events during the fest
13	Waves Controls	: organizes Waves - the cultural fest
14	Quark Controls	: organizes Quark - the technical fest
15	Spree Controls	: organizes Spree' - the sports fest
16	BITS Alumni Relations Cell	: invites alumni at the time of events

The campus also have Department of Arts, Design and Publicity (DoADP), Reception and Accommodations (RecNAcc), Paper Evaluation and Presentations (PEP), Department of Audiforce, Firewallz, *Gurukul* etc.

2.4 Student Run Organisations

S No.	Name of the Organisation	Functions
1	TEDx BITS Goa	: organizes TEDx events in the campus
2	<i>Nirmaan</i>	: helps the society and poor
3	<i>Abhigyaan</i>	: conducts classes for needy children
4	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)	: responsible for conducting IEEE events
5	Festival Committee (FestCom)	: celebrates all festivals every year

2.5 Others

S No.	Name of the Forum	Functions
1	Technology Incubator Program	: encourages innovation and incubation
2	Center for Technical Education (CTE)	: organizes classes on technical courses not included in curriculum
3	Placement Unit (PU)	: deals with placement
4	Election Commission (EC)	: responsible for conducting fair elections.

Chapter 3 | Impact of Clubs and Departments

3.1: Impact of Clubs and Departments on Academics

During the survey, most of the students, on being asked whether clubs and departments affect their CGPA, replied that student organisation affect their academic performance.

Impact on CGPA
92 responses

Figure 3.1.1 : Impact of clubs and departments on CGPA of junior undergraduates (1st and 2nd year students)

According to the survey of junior undergraduates, 9.8 % accepted that clubs and departments affected their CGPA to a great extent, 43.5% felt that they affected their CGPA to a negligible extent while 35.9 % thought that they did not affect it at all.

Impact on CGPA
31 responses

Figure 3.1.2 : Impact of clubs and departments on CGPA of senior undergraduates (3rd and 4th year students)

According to the feedback received from senior undergraduates, 35.5% believed that clubs and departments affected their CGPA to a great extent whereas 25.8 % supposed that they did not affect their CGPA at all.

Impact on CGPA
27 responses

Figure 3.1.3 : Impact of clubs and departments on CGPA of alumni

The BITS Goa alumni were also contacted for their opinion. An alumnus working at PayPal in Mumbai believed that excessive participation in club and departmental activities can have a detrimental effect on academic performance. He suggested that students should maintain a balance between academics and extracurricular activities. Another alumnus working at McKinsey & Co mentioned that students should not join too many clubs and departments, particularly if they are unable to cope up, academically. However, he also endorsed that joining a few clubs or departments (one or two) whose activities are commensurate with the interest of the students, contribute positively to academic performance. Analysis of responses received from alumni indicated that 29.6 % of them had a negligible adverse effect, with respect to participation in student organisations, on their CGPA, while 44.4 % had no effect on their CGPA at all.

The results point towards the fact that participation in too many clubs and departments can affect academic performance negatively.

3.2 Impact of Clubs and Departments on Future Prospects

Placement is the ultimate objective for every student. Clubs and departments are expected to open a land of possible business and professional meetings that can help a student during his studies or afterwards while entering the professional world.

Importance of clubs and departments in placement as compared to academic courses
92 responses

Figure 3.2.1 : Importance of clubs and departments in placement as compared to academic courses - responses by junior undergraduates (1st and 2nd year students)

As per the survey conducted, 55.4 % of junior undergraduates considered that clubs and departments are relatively less important compared to the academic courses while 31.5% believed that these setups have an equivalent role in placements, only 4.3% students were of the opinion that extracurricular are more important.

Students' expectations from clubs and departments
92 responses

Figure 3.2.2 : Students' expectations from clubs and departments - junior undergraduates (1st and 2nd year students)

When asked about their expectations from clubs and departments, 16.3% considered that they would lead to a good placement and 73.9% say that it improves their skill set.

Clubs and departments being relevant to the plan of getting a good placement package
31 responses

Figure 3.2.3 : Clubs and departments being relevant to the plan of getting good placement package - senior undergraduates (3rd and 4th year students)

When it comes to senior undergraduates, 54.8% of the students find their clubs and departments relevant to their plan of getting a good placement package.

Expected contribution of the clubs and departments in placements and internships
31 responses

Figure 3.2.4 : Expected contribution of the clubs and departments in placements and internships - senior undergraduates (3rd and 4th year students)

Almost 39% senior undergraduates indicated that clubs and departments have an average contribution in giving the skill set required for placement; 25.8% accepted that they have a significant contribution in developing soft skills while the remaining 35.5% said that they have a little contribution.

Clubs and departments being relevant to the plan of getting a good placement package
27 responses

Figure 3.2.5 : Clubs and departments being relevant to the plan of getting good placement package - alumni

However, on contacting alumni, 55.6% of alumni stated that their clubs and departments were relevant to their plan for getting a good placement, where input was from people who got placed in a variety of fields.

Contribution of clubs and departments in placements and internships
27 responses

Figure 3.2.6 : Contribution of clubs and departments in placements and internships - alumni

Regarding contribution of clubs and departments in placements, 48.1% said that the skills acquired from the clubs and departments have a high contribution in matching the required skill set of companies, 22.2% of alumni mentioned that these bodies have an average contribution; while the remaining 29.6% thought that they have a meagre contribution and that the skills acquired do not match with the skills required for placements.

3.3 Scope of Improvement in Clubs and Departments

An effort was made, to know the satisfaction level of students, and they were requested to give suggestions for the improvement of the clubs and departments.

Club and department activities overlapping with interest
92 responses

Figure 3.3.1 : Club and department activities overlapping with interest of junior undergraduates (1st and 2nd year students)

The junior undergraduates, who were a part of various clubs and departments, were asked whether the clubs and departments contented their interest. 48.9% of the students felt that the clubs and department, to which they belong, overlap completely with their interest while only 6.5% had joined clubs against their will as they could not get any other club.

The survey results also showed that 31.5% of the students spend less than 2 hours per week, 46.8% spend between 2 to 9 hours per week, and the remaining ones spend more than 9 hours per week, in clubs and departments.

Satisfaction level
14 responses

Figure 3.3.2 : Satisfaction level of senior undergraduates (3rd and 4th year students) with actions of clubs and departments

When senior undergraduates were asked whether they were satisfied with their clubs, 28.6% stated yes while 57.1% did not agree.

During the discourse, many potential suggestions came up such as creating more internship opportunities for first year and second year students, more collaborations with time, need for more guest lectures and frequent competitions, etc. A suggestion has also been given to the juniors that they should join non-technical clubs as well, for personality development.

Most of the alumni insisted on joining clubs and departments as a chance to build skill-set and to learn time management. People get to know individuals with different mind-set, learn to talk and collaborate with everyone, etc. They recommended that the clubs should have an effective management; more practical projects with more of technical content.

Chapter 4 | Effect of Clubs and Departments on Placements

4.1 Effect of Clubs and Departments on Placement as per Student Representatives of Placement Unit

After analysing the responses received from alumni, senior undergraduates, and junior graduates, a subjective feedback was taken from Placement Unit of the Institute. Two student representatives from Placement Unit were approached online. One of them, Mr. Sharma Vedant, who has been working in PU for last four years, provided a detailed scenario. According to him, “There is nothing right or wrong in joining club or departmental activities. Whether a student would gain or lose something by being part of a club, or a department, largely depends on his personal approach. However, as a rule, majority of students gain experience by being part of a bigger group and subsequently develop a network of like-minded ones.”

Leadership is another noteworthy aspect but it starts to develop when a student moves to second year of his program and acquires a coordinating position in the club or department. The trait actually gets evolved in third year, if he consistently works on a position of responsibility. In fact, clubs and departments provide one, an opportunity to learn and hone one's skills. However, a good number of students join various clubs and departments remain passive for most of the activity period and show insignificant learning. Such a practice turns futile or sometimes catastrophic to the students, during their placement.

Student's aptitude is the main factor which contributes to achieve the desired outcome. Mr. Sharma Vedant has been a part of DOCW, which helped him in becoming extrovert. He got ample opportunity to meet different people; gained managerial skills; learned event management, creative thinking and team work.

Non-technical clubs have much to offer as they provide a platform for community service and, in turn, allow a student to learn about his society, work as a team and execute his social responsibilities. But all clubs and departments do not necessarily have much to offer. One such instance is CG Club, wherein he learnt basic video editing skills and nothing significant beyond that.

In another feedback, Mr. Pateriya Pranav, a student representative from Placement Unit, presented certain new aspects pertaining to clubs and departments. According to him, participation in clubs and organizations alongside academic responsibilities allows a student to exercise not only discipline, but also time management. It also lets him to branch out and meet students outside his immediate social circle.

Clubs and departments also help a student to put his studies to practical use, while he's still learning. This provides him a lot of on-the-job experience that looks terrific on one's resume. Nevertheless, while working in clubs or departments, students often come across technical, academic or administrative barriers thereby, develops an instant problem-solving ability to resolve such issues.

Mr. Pateriya added, “Sometimes, when a student does not get placed, even after the first 3-4 weeks and every single company rejects him exponentially; neither CGPA greater than 8.5 nor summer internship placements are likely to teach him that last point. That's the moment when the practical skills and management skills help him to sustain self-confidence”.

4.2 Placements Requirements, according to Alumni

According to the alumni of BITS Goa, there is a high contribution of clubs and departments in placements, as the skills acquired through active contribution in

clubs/departments are at par with what the companies demand during placements. The scenario with internships is no different. Firms offering internships look for students who have worked under their domain and have some experience. Clubs and departments in BITS Goa ranging across domains of finance, coding, mechatronics, business consulting, infrastructure and communication cater to the requirements of different firms looking for interns. An alumnus working at McKinsey & Co., stated that companies provide due weightage to co-curricular and extra-curricular activities (sports, debates, competitions) apart from academics. Position of Responsibilities held by a student in his respective clubs and departments is a parameter for short listing of candidates. During interviews, students are frequently asked about their role in student organisations and the skills they gained from being a part of it.

Thus, project management skills, communication skills, discipline and knowledge of one's area of interest is what makes a student 'collaborative and marketable' as stated by one of the responses.

Figure 4.1.1 : Willingness of participation in clubs and departments at the cost of CGPA - alumni responses

On being asked whether they would increase or decline their participation in clubs and departments had they been given a chance, 25.9% exhibited their inclination to get involved even at the cost of CGPA whereas 51.9% were found willing but not at that cost.

Companies have certain CGPA requirements that every student has to meet, and therefore, CGPA becomes a primary focus. 29.6% of 27 alumni and 38.7% of 31 senior students seek jobs in IT companies, which prefer students with high academic record even if their extra-curricular profiles are not impressive.

The survey also emphasised the notion that regular course curriculum better identifies the placement requirements than do the clubs and departments, a fact attested by 51.9% alumni. An alumnus working at PayPal in Mumbai, stated that technical giants like PayPal and Google hire candidates with coding skills and prefer those students who have done their courses in Computer Science. Another alumnus working at Arcesium, also expressed that doing projects under a professor at BITS or any other well renowned institute in the World, is of great advantage. Letters of Recommendation (LORs) from these professors are of great help for students to fetch a job.

The most sought out for domain for placements after Computer Science is Finance. 18.5% alumni have a finance role in their companies and 22.6% of the senior students want to have a finance role in company. An alumnus, working at Goldman Sachs, said that taking up the finance minors offered by BITS was helpful for her. Taking up projects at The Wallstreet Club, which is the finance club of BITS Goa was an addition to her skills-set.

Chapter 5 | Comparison between the requirements and the view point of student on:

5.1 Academics and Main Course Curriculum

On analysis of data and corresponding discussion with alumni and all four year students, it emerges as a fact that majority of students give equal preference to academics, clubs and departments. A question was specified in survey for junior undergraduates, whether they prefer clubs and departments related to main course curriculum. Most of the students prefer those clubs and departments which are related to their main course curriculum. Their responses are indicative of the fact that they do not want to compromise with their CGPA.

Even one of the student representatives, working in placement unit, validates the fact that academic knowledge is essential to get hired for job. “Possessing a good CGPA works in favour of student but CGPA alone does not work unless he has sufficient hard and soft skills to substantiate”, he added.

5.2 Technical Aspects and Internships

Technical knowledge and internships done by students with good companies are some of the benchmarks that create a positive impact on recruiters. It increases their chances of getting placed, provided that candidate can work as a team with individuals having diverse mind-set. It also indicates that the student is familiar with the concept how a company works and is also familiar with the kind of environment he is about to enter. So, if a student has good technical knowledge and he has spent fair amount of time working as intern, then there are reasonable chances of getting a real good job, at the end.

Clubs and departments provide ample opportunities to explore their interest and work in the field of vocation. Students of 3rd and 4th year shared information about certain technical clubs like Electronics and Robotics club, Aerodynamics club, DevSoc that offer attractive projects funded by the Institute, every year. These projects are mostly led by the senior undergraduates, wherein students from 1st and 2nd years can learn under the supervision of their seniors. Besides, students learn to work as team to make the project successful.

During the present study, many students expressed an urgent need of improvement in working system. There are clubs that have good working potential to function more efficiently, as compared to what they are doing right now. Further, the Institute should allocate more funds to aid those learners who aspire to work on the projects but do not have sufficient prior knowledge, and thus, do not get a chance.

Some students also of the opinion that number of events like, quiz or interactive sessions, should be gradually increased to accommodate even more number of students in these club activities. Everyone agrees on the fact that technical aspects gained at the time working in student forum and time invested in internship ultimately pay a premium during placement.

5.3 Comparison of Requirement and Students' Viewpoint on Non-Technical Aspects

After analysing the responses received from students, it was concluded that majority of junior undergraduate students are provided with non-technical assignments in clubs and departments, irrespective of their technical or non-technical interest. However, the senior undergraduate students have a liberty to choose from technical, non- technical and managerial work.

As per the feedback of alumni and student representatives of placement unit, most of the companies include questions regarding non-technical work done by a student in their interview. A huge upsurge in self-confidence and personality is evident in those who work diligently in their clubs and departments.

It has also been noticed from the responses that during the initial years, students tend to join all sorts of technical and non-technical work in a casual manner. Such attitude is problematic, because recruiters assume that the student is interested neither to work nor to learn skills. The senior undergraduates hold positions of responsibility, which helps them taking leadership roles easier and thus taking out the fear of initiating something on their own.

Students and alumni, both agree on the point that these clubs and departments teach social networking, team management, and boost one's confidence to talk to seniors and maintain a good relationship with them. These activities provide them with overall personality and mind development which cannot be attained with a high CGPA or a high paying internship. Nonetheless, it ultimately depends upon the students how much they are willing to gain from a club or a department.

Conclusion

Taking into account the feedback and responses received from various quarters: junior undergraduates, senior undergraduate students, alumni and representatives of placement unit, it can be concluded that the students who join clubs and departments get an all-round exposure that reflects in their overall personality, which pays a rich dividend in the interview. Those, who maintain a balance between the technical and non-technical clubs and departments, are benefitted the most and have the least regrets. Only the students who hold a position of responsibility in their respective clubs and departments get acknowledged for their contribution by the company. Being active members of the clubs or departments, they are privileged to spend their time productively which leads to better learning and placement prospects.

The students, who take up practical projects in their technical clubs and departments, are equipped with creativity and hence have a cutting edge in the placements. Such projects may also help during internships by providing them with an experience beforehand.

The non-technical clubs and departments offer a wide range of managerial and leadership abilities which are of vital importance in the interviews. If students take up limited number of such clubs and departments and target the work allotted sincerely, they would imbibe these skills that would eventually help them in handling tricky situations, a skill sought by every company.

Finally, clubs and departments offer a platform to acquire different skills and abilities and if the students choose them wisely and show interest in working for the club or department without letting their technical skills and academics suffer, they would surely have better placement prospects over others.

Recommendations

From the preceding analysis and comments of the respondents, it is recommended that students should maintain a balance between technical and non-technical realms as both of them are equally important.

First year students are recommended to join clubs and departments across the available domains so that they can identify their interest and pursue those that satisfy their placement goals. As advised by the alumni, there is no use of any club or department if a student does not work, all the more it can be an obstacle in their job interviews.

It would be rewarding for students in real world, if they engage themselves more in practical projects. This provides them on-the-job experience that looks terrific on their resume. It makes the most out of their college education, because they practice what they learn. For students, at senior level, it is recommended to hold a position of responsibility (POR) which they can mention in their CV.

A word of caution for every student is that over indulgence in any club or department may affect their CGPA, which is still one of the highest priorities for placement. On campus, where student has more autonomy, one must learn to manage his schedule with academics and extracurricular activities - a skill that every employer looks for after graduation.

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Appendix

SURVEY: Impact of Clubs and Departments in Placement Scenario of BITS Goa

We are a group of first year students collecting data for our course, 'Technical Report Writing - BITS F112'. Our research focuses on the relation between clubs/depts. and placements in BITS Pilani, K.K Birla Goa Campus. All your data will be kept confidential and you can express your opinion freely. Your identity will not be revealed.

Special foci of the survey:

1. Impact of clubs and departments on academics, future prospects and their scope of improvement.
2. Effect of clubs and departments on placements according to Placement Unit and alumni.
3. Comparison between requirements and viewpoints of students on the following grounds :
 - Academics and Main Course Curriculum
 - Technical aspects and Internships
 - Non-technical skills

In the survey, three different questionnaires were floated - one for junior undergraduates (first year and second year students), another for senior undergraduates (third year and fourth year students) and a separate one for the alumni.

Questionnaire (Sample - 1)

For junior undergraduates (first year and second year students):

1. Part of which clubs and departments.
(Long answer Text)
2. Are they related to your interest?
(Multiple Choice)
3. Time spent approximately in clubs and departments per week (e.g. meetings, active participation)
(Multiple Choice)
4. How do you contribute to your club/department?
(Optional checkboxes)
5. Role/Expectations from clubs and departments:
(Optional checkboxes)
6. Do they seem to affect your CGPA?
 - Yes
 - No
 - They help in focussing on my work
7. Importance of clubs and departments compared to your academic courses for placements?
(Multiple choice)

Questionnaire (Sample - 2)

For senior undergraduates (third and fourth year students):

1. Category of companies that you plan to get placed in
(multiple choice)
2. Part of which clubs and departments
(Long answer)
3. Your role in clubs and departments
(Optional checkboxes)
4. Did you find your clubs and departments relevant to your plan for getting a good placement package?
 - Yes
 - No
5. Expected contribution of the clubs and departments in the placements and internship
(Multiple choice)
6. Do they seem to affect your CGPA?
(Multiple choice)
7. Does the regular course curriculum better identify the requirements of placements than clubs and dept.?
 - Yes
 - No
8. If given a chance, had you:
(Multiple choice)
9. Were you satisfied with actions of your clubs/departments?
 - Yes
 - No
10. If you selected No in the above question, please suggest improvements.
(Long Answer)

Questionnaire (Sample - 3)

For Alumni:

1. Category of companies that you plan to get placed in
(Multiple choice)
2. Which clubs and departments were you part of?
(Long answer)
3. Your role in clubs and departments
(Optional check boxes)
4. Did you find your clubs and departments relevant to your plan for getting a good placement package?
 - Yes
 - No
5. Contribution of the clubs and departments in the placements and internship
(Multiple choice)
6. Did they affect your CGPA?
(Multiple choice)
7. Did the regular course curriculum better identify the requirements of placements than clubs and dept.?
 - Yes
 - No
8. If given a chance, had you:
(Multiple choice)
9. Were you unsatisfied with the clubs/dept you were a part of? If so, what else could you have done?
(Long answer)